
CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK / DEFINITION

Forced Expulsion through “Release” as an Analytical Category

A Definition Document
for the Formal Fixation of the Concept
within the Analytical and Conceptual Framework

Document status:

Definition Paper

Document purpose:

To formally fix the definition of the mechanism of forced expulsion through “release,” establish the minimal set of structural elements required for its identification, define criteria of differentiation from lawful forms of release, and determine the limits of applicability of the model.

Relation to the Conceptual Framework:

This document formalizes the core definitional formula of the mechanism described in the Conceptual Framework and establishes the criteria for its correct application.

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Relation to the Analytical Report:

The empirical basis and documented cases underlying the definition are presented in the Analytical Report on forced expulsion through “release.” DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18444848>.

Relation to the Glossary:

Terminological clarification and expanded definitions of structural elements are provided in the Methodological Glossary. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18717482>

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I. Purpose and Status of the Document

This document sets out the definition of the mechanism of forced expulsion through “release” as an independent analytical category.

The document establishes the term and sets the criteria for its application:

- the definitional formula of the mechanism;
- the minimal set of its structural elements;
- the criteria for differentiation from other legal categories;
- the limits of applicability of the model.

The empirical basis is presented in the Analytical Report.

The theoretical model of the mechanism and the concept of the threshold of applicability of the normative model of release are set out in the Conceptual Framework.

The conceptual system is fixed in the Glossary.

This text does not reproduce the evidentiary material and does not provide detailed elaboration of the elements of the mechanism. The purpose of the document is to fix the definition and to establish the framework for its correct application.

II. Definitional Formula

Forced expulsion through “release” is a state-reproducible practice in which the extraction of a person from places of deprivation of liberty is used as an element of a mechanism of their subsequent physical expulsion beyond the territory of the state without:

- legal completion of the criminal status;
- termination of the execution of the sentence;
- restoration of civil and political rights;
- formalization of expulsion in a procedure established by law.

The element of coercion consists in the inevitability of return under state control in the event of refusal of expulsion.

The term “release” is used in quotation marks to indicate the discrepancy between release as the lawful termination of punishment and the factual extraction of a person from a detention facility followed by expulsion in the absence of legal completion of the criminal status.

The absence of legal completion of the criminal status means the absence of a lawful act terminating punishment (pardon, amnesty, conditional early release, review of the sentence, or another ground provided by law).

In this document, the absence of legal completion of the criminal status also includes the continued validity of the sentence in the absence of an act terminating punishment.

The elements of the mechanism are set out below as a minimal set for identification and not as separate terminological entries.

III. Minimal Set of Structural Elements of the Mechanism

3.1. Extraction from a Place of Deprivation of Liberty - removal of a person from a detention facility prior to the completion of the imposed sentence and without the adoption of a legally prescribed act terminating the criminal status.

3.2. Preservation of an Uncompleted Criminal Status - the absence of a legally prescribed act terminating punishment (pardon, amnesty, conditional early release, review of the sentence, or another lawful ground) combined with the simultaneous extraction of the person from the detention facility; the criminal status continues to operate and is not considered completed.

3.3. Short-Term Legal Uncertainty - a condition characterized by the absence of documented termination of punishment in the period between the extraction of the person from the detention facility and their actual expulsion.

3.4. Transfer to the Border - movement of the person by state authorities to the state border following extraction from the detention facility and prior to physical expulsion.

3.5. Physical Expulsion - forced crossing of the state border after extraction from the detention facility and transfer to the border, without lawful completion of the criminal status and without the possibility of remaining on the territory of the state.

3.6. Negative Alternative - a negative alternative is a situation of formal choice (to cross the border or to refuse), in which refusal of expulsion results in the removal of the person from the legal space.

Refusal to depart does not constitute a permissible legal alternative.

3.7. Closed Isolation Outside Public Determinacy (State upon Refusal) - is a situation in which a person who refuses departure is removed from the public legal space, and information concerning their whereabouts and legal status is absent.

In this condition:

- completion of the execution of the sentence is not confirmed;
- continuation of the execution of the sentence in a legally established procedure is not confirmed;
- there is no possibility of public verification of the person's legal position.

3.8. External Repression after Departure - preservation of the criminal status and legal influence of the state after the physical expulsion of the person beyond the territory of the country.

It is expressed in:

- the absence of lawful termination of punishment;
- the impossibility of safe return;
- the persistence of the threat of renewed control or prosecution.

Expulsion does not terminate repressive influence but transfers it beyond the territory of the state.

IV. Criteria for Identification of the Mechanism

The criteria for identification of the mechanism - a set of features, the simultaneous presence of which allows the qualification of a practice as forced expulsion through "release."

The minimal set of features includes:

- the absence of a legally prescribed act terminating the execution of the sentence;
- the continued validity of the sentence following the extraction of the person from the detention facility;
- the movement of the person to the state border carried out by state authorities or under their control;
- the absence of a lawful alternative to departure without return under state control or without loss of public determinacy of legal status.

The simultaneous presence of these features distinguishes this mechanism from pardon, amnesty, conditional early release, full completion of the sentence, official deportation, and other procedures formalized through an independent decision on expulsion or lawful termination of punishment.

V. Differentiation from Lawful Forms of Release

Differentiation from lawful forms of release - the establishment of the distinction between the described mechanism and:

- pardon;
 - amnesty;
 - conditional early release;
 - full completion of the sentence;
 - official deportation.
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The criterion of differentiation is the presence of a legally prescribed act terminating the execution of the sentence and the legally formalized completion of the criminal status.

Lawful forms of release presuppose the issuance of a corresponding legal act by a competent authority, its procedural formalization, and the possibility of judicial or other legally established review of the lawfulness of such a decision.

In the absence of a legally prescribed act, the termination of detention does not constitute lawful release.

VI. Limits of Applicability of the Model

The model applies in cases where the termination of factual isolation does not coincide with the legal completion of punishment and the criminal status of the person.

The model does not apply if the following are simultaneously confirmed:

- termination of the execution of the sentence in accordance with the procedure established by law;
- irreversibility of the termination of isolation on the same legal grounds;
- determinacy of the person's legal status;
- the possibility for the person to remain without the risk of renewed isolation.

Where these conditions are present, the release corresponds to the normative model and does not constitute a mechanism of forced expulsion through "release."

The list of conditions under which "the model does not apply" functions as an excluding test of the normative model of release in its minimal form.

VII. Final Provision

This definition establishes forced expulsion through "release" as an independent analytical category, distinct from lawful forms of release and formally regulated expulsion.

The definition is to be applied where the established structural elements and identification criteria set out in this document are simultaneously present.

Modification of the definitional formula is permitted exclusively in the event of changes in the structural elements of the mechanism or the loss of their reproducibility.

New empirical data shall be incorporated as supplements to the Analytical Report; terminological clarifications - in the Glossary; clarifications of the model - in the Conceptual Framework